

FELLOWSHIP

MAY 2026

Ravangla

City Vision Document

A citizen-led vision narrative capturing stories,
concerns, and hopes for the city's future

About the Vision Document

This City Vision Document is a reflective learning assignment carried out as part of the Nāgrika Fellowship Programme. It is based on a limited number of conversations with citizens and observational research conducted over a few months by the fellow. The document does not claim to represent the complete or official vision of the city, but rather offers a citizen-led snapshot—built through individual stories, insights, and lived experiences gathered during the fellowship. The perspectives shared here reflect the voices of a few residents, selected to capture a range of age groups, professions, and neighborhoods. The document is not exhaustive and may not include all communities or viewpoints. This document is intended as a starting point for dialogue and reflection. We hope it encourages broader conversations about the city’s identity, challenges, and future possibilities.

The research and writing were undertaken independently by the fellow, within a framework of structured guidance provided by Nāgrika. This included thematic prompts, narrative-building exercises, regular mentorship and feedback sessions, all designed to support the fellow in shaping their city’s vision. The interpretations and final content remain those of the fellow.

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Nāgrika Fellowship

The **Nāgrika Fellowship Programme** has been designed to empower young individuals from diverse educational and geographic backgrounds, including students, gap-year participants, and early-career researchers, to positively engage with the history, socio-economic, governance, and cultural context of their cities. Focused on the youth of small and mid-sized cities, the fellowship is building local knowledge, enabling civic consciousness, and developing thought leaders who can address environmental, social, and infrastructural challenges. Over a period of six months, fellows gained tools for understanding and engaging with their cities.

A key component of the fellowship is the development of the **City Vision Document** by the fellows. This document is an emotionally grounded reflection of how citizens experience and imagine their city. Developed through conversations with diverse residents of the fellows' cities, it weaves together stories of everyday life, places of belonging, pressing concerns, and aspirations for the future. The document captures lived experiences and heartfelt insights to build a narrative that is authentic, accessible, and community-driven. It serves not only as a record of local voices but also as an invitation to reimagine the city through the eyes of those who call it home.

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Everyday Life

This theme explores the daily rhythms, routines, and interactions that shape how people experience their city. It highlights the ordinary yet meaningful details of our city's life and how citizens connect with their surroundings on a regular basis.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging are spaces that hold emotional, cultural, or social significance for residents. This theme focuses on spaces that provide identity, memory, and a sense of home, the places where we feel connected, seen, and grounded.

Voices of Concern

This theme brings out the issues and challenges that citizens face in their day-to-day lives such as poor infrastructure, lack of public transport, disappearing green spaces, water or waste management issues, safety concerns, or loss of cultural heritage.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow reflects citizens' aspirations for the city's future. This theme brings forward ideas, hopes, and solutions imagined by the people who live in and care for the city.

Why this Vision Document?

A City Vision Document helps capture a city, the way it runs, changes happening along the way, future aspirations, vision and so on. This CVD is different since the locals are part of the process chosen for making this document happen. I, as a fellow of Nagrika from Ravangla, and the people of Ravangla, as the interviewee; as the storyteller of Ravangla, are part of this CVD along with the Nagrika Organisation, which has provided plenty to make this document happen. This document is not just a formal record of a geographical place called ‘Ravangla’, but it is a conscious attempt to record Ravangla as a living, breathing and changing place, where people live and grow together. In a changing world, where everything seems the same but somehow different the next day, it feels very important to capture places and cities we come from, cities we call home, not just as a data document, citing physical features of a place, but narrating stories about actual life in an attempt to transport the reader into this small city called Ravangla. We all have this feeling of wanting a chance to write our own stories, not anyone writing them for us, instead ‘us’ as part of the process, the vision and narrator of our realities. Hence, this city vision document binds us, the people of Ravangla, because we all have contributed to it. Importantly, we shared our voices of concern and dreams we have for Ravangla.

Meet Ravangla

The earliest depiction of Ravangla that I have heard was through my grandmother, who narrated, recollecting her past, that Ravangla was filled with pine trees and jungle everywhere, with nearly two or three wooden houses. She said that the Himalayan Black Bear used to roam in the jungle; it is still sighted in Ravangla from time to time, but now the bears are said to live in the Maenam hill area, which is adjacent to Ravangla. The locals describe Ravangla as a very unpredictable place weather-wise. I recollect one of the uncles in Ravangla describing this feature as “रवाङ्गला मान्छेको मन जस्तै छ।” which means “Ravangla is like a human heart”. Sometimes Ravangla is sunny, bright and cheerful like a happy person's heart and the city is filled with birds chirping, people out under the sun, cleaning, dusting, pickle jars taken out, locals talking and so on. Other times, Ravangla is gloomy with no sound at all, except for the moving vehicles, then it feels like the whole world is in slow motion, slowly going on about life. There are also days when the cloud thunders as if it is angry and showers rain like there is no tomorrow, people turn off their electric appliances and share stories, jokes, and weather remarks to lighten their hearts together with hot tea. You can witness the whole spectrum of weather during summertime in Ravangla. Winter here, on the other hand, grows chilly with sharp winds flowing straight from the icy mountains, but it is in this season when the sky and the forest open up, leeches disappear (thankfully), and the trek enthusiasts can finally go to Maenamla and Bhaleydhunga Wildlife Reserve, people come from Bhutan and all over Sikkim to go enjoy hot springs of Borong and Polok via Ravangla and tourists slowly enter the city to watch the mountains.

INTRODUCTION

The people of Ravangla are asked one question, time and again, by the visitors who come here, “Apko thand nahi lagta’ (Don’t you feel cold?), to which the locals simply reply with a smile, ‘Abb toh adat ho chuka isiliyeh hameh yahi peh accha lagta hai. Santi hai yaha” (Now we are used to Ravangla and its weather, that’s why we like it here. Peace is here). Peace and Ravangla feel synonymous to me, Ravangla is peaceful, or peace is in Ravangla, both describe this place I call home. Some locals like it for its peacefulness, and some escape it because it is ‘too peaceful’. This peace is not something that is bestowed upon us, but it is maintained through the way of life led by the locals, through the traditions and costumes which relentlessly try to maintain peace, compassion and harmony, through the small and big acts of locals. Around four to five in the morning, you will hear birds chirping, and the whole city wakes up by 7-8 and starts with their daily activities. Some rush to their schools, some to their offices, shopkeepers sweeping in front of their shops to tidy up, the city beautifiers already on their way home after preparing the city for its people.

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Chya or Chai in Ravangla means both tea and alcohol. Since Ravangla is a cold place, some adults finish their day with alcohol, which, according to them, ‘makes their blood run faster and warms up their body’. Hence, after some sips or gulps of alcohol, the day in Ravangla officially ends at 8 pm with the sharp whistles from police personnel, and the shopkeepers close their shops, except for the pharmacy stores. This is something that the tourists find peculiar about Ravangla, ‘Itna jaldi bazaar band hojata hain’, they say, to which the locals reply ‘Yaha peh thanda hain na isiliyeh’. The weather here really influences the daily life of the residents of Ravangla; you will always find the locals walking with a jacket in the market even on days when it's warm enough for a t-shirt. One local shopkeeper aunty jokingly said, “It is good for us when Ravangla is cold since people buy more clothes”. Ravangla is a big community, it feels like a *Gemeinschaft* (community) as described by Ferdinand Tonnues, who introduced the dichotomy of *Gemeinschaft* (Community) and *Gesellschaft* (Association). People here know each other, directly or indirectly, and in challenging times, they stand up for each other. There are samaj covering specific areas of Ravangla, they are organised together to help each other in both good times (like marriage or any ceremony) and in challenging times (like landslide, sickness, funeral and so on).

In hilly areas, an individualistic way of living feels absurd; the community way of life is not just embedded in the traditions and customs practised here but also in daily practices. Maybe one day Ravangla might also turn into a *Gesellschaft* (Association) found in big cities, but for now it consists of a big community of the locals of Ravangla, through both the best and worst of times.

Character of the City

Ravangla is nestled in the midst of green valleys, rolling hills and mountains. Mt. Kanchenjunga, Mt. Pandim, Mt. Siniolchu and Mt. Kabru are visible from Ravangla. In Sikkim, nature is deeply embedded in the culture of all the communities living here, especially the Lepcha community, who are known to be the original inhabitants of Sikkim. ‘Pang lhabsol’ is an important festival of Sikkim, celebrated annually, with grandeur and honour in Ravangla, to worship Mt. Kanchenjunga and the deities for protection. This festival is very important for Sikkim because, along with being a celebrated festival, it is also an important event celebrated for the remembrance and reaffirmation of unity among Sikkim’s indigenous communities.

Along with the festival, other activities like volleyball tournaments and local stalls are organised in Ravangla to boost local business and to create a social space for all communities. Simultaneously, other festivals are observed by the locals, like Losar and Losoong of communities like Bhutia, Lepcha, Sherpa, Tamang and Gurung, Chasok Tangnam by the Limboo-Limbu-Subba community, Sakewa by the Rai community, and Dasai by the Nepali communities, etc. Diwali, Holi, and Christmas are also celebrated with love by the locals. People here have a strong bond with each other. During the festival season, locals invite each other and celebrate together. The overall socio- cultural life in Ravangla, as in Sikkim, is based on the foundation of unity since we have people from different communities and ethnic groups. The diversity and harmony of Ravangla add more charm to this place, which is already beautiful because of nature.

INTRODUCTION

Ravangla acts as a centre economic hub for surrounding village areas, back in the days people used to come here to sell their cardamom harvest but it declined later on, but what remained was the established ‘Ration dokan’ (Ration Shop), Haat Bazaar or Lal Bazaar area where every week the ‘dokanee’ brings their things to sell, the farmers bring their seasonal harvest to sell and also to buy essentials from the shops to bring back home. There is a khata system, a system of taking things on loan to pay later on, which is recorded in the khata of ration shop owners. This is followed even now. Many shopkeepers from the village area and the locals buy things from ration shops following the khata system, built on trust and community life, which is slowly evolving daily.

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This system is not just limited to the ration shops, but it is also practised by the hotels, the paan dokaan (Paan Shop), the clothing shops and so on. This system is not possible in a market area which has evolved or is evolving fast, since the building of community takes time, community as in, everyone knows each other; there is space for accountability if the dues are not paid, the trust among people are there, and the feeling of belonging is established through it.

Personal Connection to the City:

My parents shifted to Ravangla, from Barmelli, which is 1 hour away, to enrol me in nursery school. Ever since I grew up in Ravangla, completed my schooling and shifted to other places for higher education, but no matter how big or convenient other places felt, I have always been attached to Ravangla. The attachment, I thought, was a result of my growing up here (which is true), but beyond that, the way this city feels to me plays an important factor on the love and attachment I have for this place. I remember thinking out loud how, no matter which big city I live in, my heart will always yearn for Ravangla. The quietness, the slow-moving nature of this place, nature, hills and so on, make me feel like myself. Ravangla is a place you come to when you want to listen to your self- to know yourself.

Everyday Life

Everyday Life

Conversation among the people of Ravangla begins with weather topics like ‘Aju kasto jado cha hai?’ (It’s so cold today, right?) and then the chit-chat transcends many topics. Well, Ravangla is known for its crisp winter weather, which is very unpredictable, especially during summer, so you will find the locals with an extra pair of jacket or sweatshirt tucked somewhere, even during peak summer. When I was a kid, I heard someone defining this city as ‘Ravangla chai manche ko maan jastai cha’, meaning that this city (and its weather) is like a human heart; very unpredictable. Sometimes the sun is up, nice and warm, then suddenly it’s gloomy with fog. The climate here is very challenging, so the locals have to be on high alert, especially the shopkeepers and vegetable sellers. People here are very friendly and kind-hearted. In a small city like Ravangla, everyone knows each other, whether it’s because they know each other directly or indirectly. The locals have a very simple lifestyle here, with daily routine patterns of getting started for the day, managing business, attending school, or running a shop. In their free time, the locals go on a walk to the Buddha Park area, or the Cho Zho Lake area, or they socialise in the Bazar area.

The day starts early with most of the locals up and about at around 6 am or 7 am. During morning time, you will experience fresh winds flowing straight from the mountains, which assuredly chase away any sleepiness within you. Shopkeepers will be cleaning their stores for the day, restaurant owners preparing food, city beautifiers already returning home after beautifying the city for its people, drivers ready beside their cars waiting for their passengers and the dogs (the main locals of any city) sleeping where the sun rays fall. The day begins calmly in Ravangla, slowly mellowing down for the RUSH HOUR, from 8:30- 10 am, when most people rush to their offices, schools, or any work. After this, the city again quiets down, everything feels steady and slow as if the whole of Ravangla is in neutral mode. Bustle again begins around 3-4 pm when the school closes down, students cheerfully returning home, office goers shopping in the market, you will hear laughter and cheers and hurried movements around this time. The main bazaar then closes at 8 pm (apart from the medical shops) with sharp whistles blown by the local police who guard Ravangla even during the coldest winter nights. Peace here is not just maintained via climate and nature, but it is also maintained by its people. Locals love how peaceful this place is, even though some locals expressed that Ravangla is slower compared to other cities. However, they still wished for peace to remain in this place.

Declining in-person meetings

The treasurer of the local Samaj and member of the local SHG (Self-Help Group), who runs a shop and manages a home, replied, ‘My daily routine is normal.’ Most of the interviewees replied, ‘My routine is normal (ordinary)’; they must have felt that it was boring, with nothing extraordinary about it. However, it showed us a glimpse of how locals live in Ravangla. When I went to do the interview, she was in front of her shop, with her phone, enjoying the warm sun. She runs a sports shop, which initially was a stationery shop, but due to less business, she shifted her shop towards sports equipment. As the interview resumed further, she expressed how she has noticed a decline in people meeting together for casual meetups or for spending time. She said that this might be because everyone is busy in their life now, busy with work, and because of technologies like phones, people prefer to call each other instead of having face-to-face meetings. She expressed this, with an internal realisation, that she herself too thought about declining meetups as the interview went on. So this statement came with a self-realisation from her and an explanation, that, ‘When you start getting busy at home, outings and meeting people start to decline. Now everyone is busy with their own life, so we rarely meet nowadays compared to when we were young.’

Badminton to video games

At the beginning of the interview, the responses of the interviewee were very mundane and dry, which reflected that he thought his everyday routine was boring and uninteresting, perhaps. Gradually, as the conversation went on and the topic of badminton came forth, he expressed deep feelings and expectations.

A **recent passout student**, preparing for JEE Mains, said I don't do anything extra, just in my home, helping out, studying, playing games and other usual stuff. As the interview went on, covering questions of things **he used to do, he expressed how he used to go play badminton, which he wanted to pursue professionally too, but stopped now, since there were and there still are no coaches in Ravangla. This statement came with a hint of disappointment about how he had expected things to change, a coach to come to Ravangla, but this didn't change, and now his badminton learning has ceased to be a hobby as well.** He opened up that he was very enthusiastic about badminton; he used to wake up early, but now he just stays at home preparing for his exams, playing video games and meeting friends sometimes, when they come back for holidays. Since most of his friends have already enrolled in colleges and educational institutions outside of Ravangla.

The experience of this student is not an individual one, but rather reflects a broader structural pattern which impacts the psychological behaviours of youths living in smaller cities. The discontinuation of badminton, which the interviewee wanted to pursue seriously, due to the absence of a coach, is not an individual experience. **This experience is described by Amartya Sen in his capability approach, which addresses that individuals often internalise the limitations that challenge the development of their interests and abilities so deeply that they stop wanting to execute them.** Hence, they think that what they want to do is undoable. The external environment is often the reason for this pattern of discouragement among youths.

His experience of leaving his hobby and hooking up to video games is an example which reflects the impact of the structural environment on the psychological development of individuals. As the interview went on, he expressed that in the future, he wants to see a change in this factor; he wants the availability of coaches and the availability of structural needs in the city.

Town for peace, cities for convenience:

An interviewee who recently shifted from Ravangla to Siliguri stated that she misses the 'peace' she felt living in Ravangla. Everything feels fast and chaotic in Siliguri, where you have to be alert at all times. Comparing Siliguri with Ravangla, she stated that Ravangla lacks many things because of which Siliguri is far more convenient to live, having good hospitals, malls, big markets and so on. However, she concluded that she feels free and at peace in Ravangla. When probed about which place she wants to be in, she answered that "Ravangla is a place I feel free and fully myself, even though it is not as convenient as living in Siliguri."

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This made us, both the interviewee and I, realise that life is easy in Siliguri, very convenient in all aspects, but the lack of peace makes one yearn for a place which lacks convenience.

Need for urban planning in hill cities, especially in the transitioning towns

Like most of the hill cities, Ravangla also witnesses the issue of narrow roads and parking issues, since most of the vehicles, both taxi and private vehicles, are parked at the side of roads. Most of the interviewees stated that they have to stay alert while walking or crossing roads. While walking, their pace is disrupted by parked vehicles, which causes slight frustration. **A senior citizen** stated that even though he had a leg surgery, he prefers to walk his way around the city. He expresses his love for nature and prefers to walk a walkable distance with his cane, but he feels frustrated because of the parked vehicles on the sides of the road, which makes it hard to walk freely and demands him to stay alert.

From 'Strict Rules' to 'No Rules'

Talking on this topic, the **local reporter** stated that the parking issue can be stopped with the steady application of regulatory policies, like the traffic rules, but the problem persists because notices are issued by the authorities, but the application of these notices is not observed steadily. The SDM of Ravangla, along with the Bazar Committees have tried solving these issues by issuing official notices; mandating the vehicles to utilise the parking lot, which is deserted since it is 1 km downward from the market, making it isolated from the bazar area, but the notices are observed for some days, and afterwards the parking problem resumes again. **Irregularity in regulatory policies can lead to people taking laws and regulations for granted, making it very hard to solve persistent problems.**

Most of the interviewees stated that when they are free, they go visit the Buddha Park and Cho Zho Lake area since they feel at peace and free there. They love the serene nature there, so to unwind, they take a stroll there. Individuals who grew up and studied in Ravangla visit their school ground area, as it brings back nostalgia for their school memories.

Most of the **young individuals** stay at home instead of going out in their daily routine, as they expressed, because their friends have shifted to other places for education or work. They go for walks around the Buddha Park and Cho Zho Lake area, but apart from that, most of the young individuals rarely go out. The older generation has also seen a decline in face-to-face meetings since they are busy with their work or business and prefer phone conversations. **A Teacher** working in Ravangla also stated that 'I used to meet people, but now many of them are busy and such gatherings have become less frequent'.

Structural analysis

Decline in outdoor meetings

The older generation stated that most of them are busy in their life and prefer to keep in touch via phone nowadays. Some stated that they have seen a decline in face-to-face meet-ups because of busy lives and because of technologies like phones, which, for some, is the cause of fewer face-to-face meet-ups, and for some, is the cause of virtual modes of communication. The responders first stated that the decline is because of technologies like phones, and while elaborating on it, they mentioned that for them too, virtual communication has become convenient. Since they have to plan meetings indoors, in someone's home or a restaurant, just dialling a number or using a video call is more convenient for them. Lack of public spaces with benches can also be noted here, since most of the unplanned meetings were mentioned to be in the Lal Bazaar areas, according to the locals. There are no resting areas in the market, so the meetups, with long conversations, can only happen inside restaurants and hotels or at someone's house.

The Buddha Park areas are a bit far from the main market area, so these places were noted as 'places they visited when they were free'. To elaborate more on this, I would like to compare the urban space of Ravangla with the urban spaces of Namchi and Gangtok. Namchi has Centre Park and Gangtok has Mahatma Gandhi Marg, both of which are spacious, have a lot of sitting area, including benches, and facilities like 'private enclosed areas for breastfeeding made for mothers'. Both of these areas in the past were identical to the present bazaar area of Ravangla; functioning roads were there in the M.G. marg and Centre Park area, but now additional roads and a traffic layout have been made to make the park area vehicle-free and tiled completely for locals. This is an example, from Sikkim, which shows us that the construction of such spaces is possible in Ravangla too. Economically, both of the mentioned areas from Namchi and Gangtok were commercial successes, which not just helped Namchi and Gangtok to grow as commercial and tourist sites, but also gave a space for locals to enjoy their city fully. In Ravangla, the locals go to the bazaar area for work reasons, and the conversations are cut short, especially during busy hours of the day.

The younger generation of interviewees stated that most of their friends have moved out for work opportunities or for higher education. Those who did the interviewees are preparing for exams, or working here, so they stated that they meet their friends sometimes at the bazar area, or the Buddha Park area. This can also be the reason why youngsters spend less time outside here. The demographic gap can also be a reason, as described above, since if you take a stroll around, most of the locals in the market area belong to the older generation. One interviewer stated that since Ravangla is a small place, everyone knows each other, so in that sense, the young generation does not feel as free, and they do not get the space to grow.

Narrow spaces in the Market Area

Ravangla Bazar, compared to other bigger cities in Sikkim, like Namchi and Gangtok, do not have a bazaar hub area which is as planned and structurally made as the Mahatma Gandhi Marg (in Gangtok) and the Centre Park (in Namchi). The main road is situated in the middle of Ravangla, with shops on

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either side. The left side has footpaths, and if you enter the Lal Bazar area on the left side of the road, there is a spacious walking space, where vehicles do not enter.

However, there are no benches as of now, so the locals hurry their conversations or move towards the nearby hotels to relax and converse. The younger generation might feel left out in this setup since they do not have access to money for cafes or hotel meets every day, making their school ground or front yard the only accessible spaces to play and spend their time apart from school and home. Areas like the Buddha Park area, Cho Zho lake area and the helipad area were frequently stated as places the locals visit when they are free. However, these areas are a bit far from the main market area, so they visit only when they are free. When answering the question about 'places where conversations naturally happen', most of them replied the bazaar area, especially on Sundays when the market opens fully, with local farmer vegetable shops and the haat bazar.

Unused Plaza and persisting parking issue

As mentioned above, the parking problem in Ravangla is the result of the unused plaza, which is isolated from the market. This makes the roads of Ravangla narrower, making it very congested and difficult for pedestrians. The construction of public infrastructures away from the market area came with a vision that if constructions happen in the outskirts of the bazaar area, then that place will develop too. The construction of the plaza on Yangyang road, according to the vision, was supposed to develop that area of Ravangla, because the cars would be parked there, so many shops might open and so on, but as I have mentioned, Ravangla already has established ration shops and bazaar area, plus the khata system, which limits the commercial activities in the main market area. Furthermore, the anticipated change did not follow up after the plaza started functioning, the vehicles still park in the main bazaar and complain that the plaza is too far. Now no one can move that plaza in the market area, nor can the market shift to the plaza area, so the parking problem persists, while efforts to use the plaza show slow progress. This makes the locals think that urban planning, the study of an area and then the execution of plans are necessary for the growth and benefit of Ravangla.

A mother plus shopkeeper stated that in addition to the parked vehicles, the ongoing constructions in buildings which are located beside the footpath or the roads seem very risky since they are not properly sealed, demanding them to be alert when walking. The parking problem persists because, despite efforts made to solve it, the solutions are not applied uniformly and regularly, resulting in irregular application of regulatory policies, which also results in unserious response from the public whenever actions are implemented.

Reflection

What does this reveal about the city?

The decline in outdoor meetings reflects the demographic gap in Ravangla, where most of the youngsters have shifted out of the city, most of them temporarily, making the remaining young generation spend most of their time inside their homes. Lack of coaches in sports courts is making young individuals approach video games more and not pursue sports professionally.

Even the older generation has started to meet each other less because of busy schedules, and the alternative of a virtual mode of communication makes it more convenient to call than to meet in person. Lack of community parks in the bazaar area, where no cars are allowed, like the centre park in Namchi, can also be a cause for this decline, for all generations. Since we can see people of all generations spending time at Center park, where they are seen sitting on the benches reading newspapers, on their phones, some just sitting, and some talking to each other. This is something we do not see in Ravangla Bazaar. In the Buddha Park, there is space, but it is far from the market area, and people only go there when they are free. Another reason why we do not see people spending time in the Bazaar area, as we do in Namchi, is because of the narrow roads and parking issues.

This reveals that there is a need for a space, a public space, for people to meet in the bazaar area. A need for the Bazaar area to be more pedestrian and locally friendly, a place people don't go for work but for other purposes or no purposes at all. I feel this is very crucial to building bonding between the locals and the city.

If policymakers understood this, they would realise....

If policymakers come and live in the city first, study it, study the patterns and routines of the local people, then only they would realise where changes are needed and where they are not needed. Ravangla has a community centre, a library, and a plaza, but they are constructed so far from the bazar area that people have to schedule a separate time to visit them. Most of the people don't even know that there is a plaza, a community centre, or a public library, making both those places and the locals isolated from it. If the policy makers studied this place properly, then alternative solutions, better plans would have been executed, benefiting both the locals and the public authorities. The unused public spaces mean a loss for both the public and the government.

Places of Belonging

Places of Belonging

Buddha Park and the Cho Zho Lake area

Most of the interviewees stated that they visit these areas, which are near to each other, whenever they are free because they feel at peace here and the natural scenes are beautiful to enjoy. Most of the older generation associated this area with their childhood, when it was a forest area, untouched by any construction plans. One interviewee stated that they used to go to the forest to gather wild vegetables, some used to go to hang out, some stopped there while visiting Ravangla, since it acted as an important cardamom trading point back then, so people from the nearby villages brought their cardamom produce there by foot to sell it and stopped around the forest areas to rest.

The School Area

Most of the individuals who studied here talked about how their school area is an important part of their childhood and adolescence, since they used to hang out there. They reflected that when they visit their school, they get flashbacks of their past. Most of the interviewees were pass-out students of PM Shrii Victoria Cross Ganju Lama Senior Secondary School, which is located right beside the Main Market line of Ravangla. PM Shri VCGL has a big compound with a big school ground, where most of the football tournaments and town celebrations, including the yearly celebration, which is Independence Day, have happened in the past. Right now, the ground is undergoing construction to make it better. Many youngsters, who were interviewed, also shared attachments with Little Scholars Academy and Sikkim Public School, stating that they still go to the school compounds because it reminds them of their childhoods.

Maenam Wildlife Sanctuary

Most of the older interviewees stated that they used to trek here, but now they do not because of health issues. One interviewee stated that this place, known for its wildlife and natural beauty, should be left alone without any artificial construction, as this would affect the flora and fauna of that place. There is a big tourism boost project happening there, targeting tourism in Ravangla-Yangyang, by making skywalks and ropeways at Maenam and BhaleyDhunga.

Nature and peace are prioritised by the locals a lot since people from all ethnic groups worship nature in one way or another. The annual festival of Pang Lhabsol worships and honours Mt Kanchenjunga; other communities worship nature through their respective festivals. These traditions are deeply rooted in the culture of the locals and make them very wary and alert about development, which seems, to them, comes with the price of peace and nature. This leads to a deeper question of 'Is there an alternative way to bring development while still holding on to peace?'

PLACES OF BELONGING

What is affecting these places?

Development pressure

Since tourism is the source of revenue for Sikkim, we have witnessed a lot of tourism boosting projects targeting connectivity with bigger roads, construction of urban structures like malls, construction of tourism sites and so on. The development pressure is more on tourism sites because of this, each place is transforming to appeal more to the tourists, for example, in the Buddha Park, food stalls have multiplied, homestays and hotels have grown, and more tourist-targeted things are coming up. Comparing this development with the bazaar area of Ravangla, we can see a huge gap. We can see no structural change in the bazaar area. The tourist site of Buddha Park has two parking sites, one being constructed in the Cho Zho Lake area, while in the market, vehicles are parked here and there, with an unused plaza 1 km away from the market. There hasn't been any bigger change in the market areas except for the local farmer stalls set up by the Horticulture Department. Observing these gaps makes one feel that the changes in the city are happening more for tourist appeal rather than for the locals.

Neglect

Neglect in the back-to-back construction of public spaces without planning or vision is concerning. Where are the locals supposed to go in the market? "Work and back home. Repeat" are the answers of the interviewees.

Regulations

Regulations, as mentioned above, should be applied uniformly and steadily to solve persisting problems.

Changing lifestyles

People are spending more time inside their homes rather than meeting people outside. The decline in outdoor meetings reflects the demographic gap in Ravangla, where most of the youngsters have shifted out of the city, most of them temporarily, making the remaining young generation spend most of their time inside their homes. Plus, the bazaar area is visibly neglected compared to the tourist sites, making the locals prefer their homes more than the public spaces.

PLACES OF BELONGING

Reflection

Who feels welcome? Who doesn't?

There are many sites for tourists, many spaces for them, but the locals have to face the same narrow roads they did years ago, the same drainage problems, the same no-bench market where they go for some work, come back and repeat. The younger generation is moving out, while the remaining stay stuck at home. The older generations are switching towards virtual modes of communication rather than face-to-face meetings, which can also be seen as a result of frustrating pathways.

Development here should be careful because this place carries...

Development in the forested areas should be careful because Nature for the locals holds deep cultural and emotional significance. Development should not come with the price of chaos and disruption of peace, as per the locals who expressed concerns about developments, as seen in Siliguri, where things are accessible and convenient but chaotic.

Voices of Concern

Voices of Concern

Lack of spaces

Most of the young individuals who were interviewed stated that they do not spend much time outside. If they go out, it's either for some work or chores. The same is with the older generation, they are busy with their work plus they mentioned that meeting people has decreased over the years. Decline in outdoor meetings: The older generation stated that most of them are busy in their life and prefer to keep in touch via phone nowadays. Some stated that they have seen a decline in face-to-face meet-ups because of busy lives and because of technologies like phones, which, for some, is the cause of fewer face-to-face meet-ups, and for some, is the cause of virtual modes of communication.

The younger generation of interviewees stated that most of their friends have moved out for work opportunities or for higher education. Those who did the interviewees are preparing for exams, or working here so they stated that they meet their friends sometimes at the bazaar area, or the Buddha Park area, this can also be the reason why youngsters spend less time outside here. The demographic gap can also be a reason, as described above, since if you take a stroll around, most of the locals in the market area are the older generation. One interviewer stated that since Ravangla is a small place, everyone knows each other so in that sense the young generation does not feel as free, and they do not get the space to grow.

Narrow spaces in the Market Area

Ravangla Bazar, compared to other bigger cities in Sikkim, like Namchi and Gangtok, do not have a bazaar hub area which is as planned and structurally made as the Mahatma Gandhi Marg and the Centre Park. The main road is situated in the middle of Ravangla, with shops on either side. The left side has footpaths, and if you enter the Lal Bazar area on the left side of the road, there is a spacious walking space, where vehicles do not enter. However, there are no benches as of now, so the locals hurry their conversations or move towards the nearby hotels to relax and converse.

The younger generation might feel left out in this setup since they do not have access to money for cafes or hotel meets every day, making their school ground or front yard the only accessible spaces to play and spend their time apart from school and home. Areas like the Buddha Park area, Cho Zho lake area and the helipad area were frequently stated as places the locals visit when they are free. However, these areas are a bit far from the main market area, so they visit only when they are free. When answering the question about 'places where conversations naturally happen', most of them replied the bazaar area, especially on Sundays when the market opens fully, with local farmer vegetable shops and the haat bazar.

VOICES OF CONCERN

Unused Plaza and persisting parking issue

As mentioned above, the parking problem in Ravangla is the result of the unused plaza, which is isolated from the market. This makes the roads of Ravangla narrower, making it very congested and difficult for pedestrians. A mother plus shopkeeper stated that in addition to the parked vehicles, the ongoing constructions in buildings which are located beside the footpath or the roads seems very risky since they are not properly sealed, demanding them to be alert when walking. The parking problem persists because, despite efforts made to solve it, the solutions are not applied uniformly and regularly, resulting in irregular application of regulatory policies, which also results in unserious response from the public whenever actions are implemented.

Drainage problem and potholes

A shopkeeper and a student, who manages her family hotel temporarily, mentioned that the drainage problem has remained persistent over the years, with no sign of improvement. This leads to overspilling of drain water on the roads during the monsoon season, which damages the roads, and the locals face problems because of it. The student mentioned that roads get damaged very much during the monsoon season, making it hard for students like her to come back home. Most of them don't come home very much during the monsoon season.

Concern for nature

Most of the locals in Ravangla, especially those who have spent their childhood in this region, expressed deep concerns for changes in the environment and nature of Ravangla. They recollected how there used to be sal trees at a particular area, which is now full of buildings, while some recollected fields of cardamom in between Kewzing to Ravangla, which has now declined, and one local shared his observation of the decline in varieties of birds which used to be here before.

Hesitation towards development

A regular pattern that came forward from the interview was their hesitation towards development. The locals want development; they acknowledge that change is inevitable and essential. In addition, they had a vision for the future of Ravangla; a developed city with cleanliness, with availability of essential things and services, a facilitated hospital and so on. However, their hesitation came from the lived reality they have seen from other developed or developing cities, where nature has borne the price, peace has disappeared, crime rates have gone up, water shortage, lack of urban planning and so on. This is the side of development that the locals fear, because of which some even expressed that Ravangla is better the way it is, even if it is underdeveloped.

VOICES OF CONCERN

Citizen Quotes

“Natural things should not be transformed into artificial things”

- A local who works at Ravangla.

“People try, but things don’t happen. Things like colleges and hospitals, we have a small PHC, but we need good, hospitable and educational institutions so that we don’t have to travel to other places for everything. We face the effects of this issue in all aspects, money, time and tiredness because we have to travel together to places for healthcare and education.”

-A local shopkeeper at Ravangla

“Because of the unavailability of coaches in Ravangla despite having a badminton court, we have gradually stopped expecting change.”

-A recent class 12 passout who spends most of his time inside his house.

“In the bazaar area, there is a traffic problem; vehicles are parked everywhere, so people like us, who have to walk, face a lot of problems because of it. There is a car plaza here, but the cars and other vehicles are not parked there; instead, they park in the bazaar area.”

-A local who loves walking to his office every day despite challenges

“I feel that Ravangla is manifesting into an unplanned city, I feel that the city and its infrastructure are not systematically made, as far as I know. Parking and car plaza are examples.”

-A local

“Lack of good institutions for higher education. Students often have to go outside for their further studies.”

-A student who is studying outside of Ravangla.

“I feel that the issue persists because the people who are responsible for its solution do not try to solve it seriously; they listen to the problems, show interest for a short time, and then the issue is forgotten.”

“We don’t know the agencies and bodies that plan the infrastructure that are lying unused, so I feel that they should collectively work together to solve these issues.”

“This concern persists because people are not telling anything about these problems, or the government is not taking them very seriously.”

“People don’t express this problem; those who can pay go to other places, those who cannot manage anyhow, so the problem remains without any change while people adjust to it”.

“People adjust, like there are solutions to all problems, but people just keep to themselves”.

VOICES OF CONCERN

Emerging patterns across interviews

Specific people groups

Youth concerns, Women's concerns, etc.

Youth Concerns

Availability of spaces for socialising, playing sports, coaches and other needed things.

Safe space

Sikkim is a safe place, but dark alleys and pathways feel intimidating and scary for everyone. An interviewer said 'She wants her children to grow up in a town where they don't have to worry about rushing home early because the street lights to their home don't work'.

Local concern

They don't want to lose the 'Peaceful Ravangla' which they 'belong to' for development.

Civic complaints

Governance gaps, Environmental concerns
Local media narratives.

Reflection

What concerns does this highlight about issues within the city?

The major concerns of Ravangla, like the drainage problems or the narrow roads, are experienced by all the locals. Other niche concerns like the unavailability of coaches, socialising centres with opportunities to grow as a person, working street lights, and nature are concerns that vary from person to person. Still, each of these concerns shows us the spectrum of discomfort and problems that the locals face, which makes the vacuum spaces of growth and needed changes in Ravangla.

What is systemic vs what is incidental?

Nature-induced disasters, like landslides and blockage of roads, are incidental, but drainage problems and over-spilling of water on roads during the monsoon season are systemic problems. This problem is not new; it has been experienced by the locals for many, many years. The drainage is the same, and the problem has remained 'THE SAME'. Population growth is incidental, but the need for proper town planning, proper Urban planning, is something we, the people of Ravangla, should focus on from now. Unrepaired streetlights and a lack of coaches are systemic problems which should not remain persistent.

Dreams for Tomorrow

Dreams for Tomorrow

The people of Ravangla hope to preserve the nature and culture of this place because the identity of Ravangla is linked with it. The Buddha Park area is well-loved by the locals because it is peaceful, clean, and full of nature. These are the characteristics that people link with the identity and vibe of the city. Youths of Ravangla want change but not at the cost of peace or nature.

“I hope people here don’t change, I hope their empathetic and civil behaviour won’t change”

“I hope Ravangla is clean, safe and law & order is maintained in this city”

“I hope that the environment remains the same as today, clean and healthy”

“I hope that the greenery does not change. Looking at Gangtok and Ravangla, Ravangla is still green; It is quiet. Gangtok is overpopulated. I don’t want that to change in Ravangla in the upcoming days.”

“I hope this city will never be run by some private company; it should be free for everyone, especially for locals.”

“I want change to come, it is needed, but the cultural and historic things of Ravangla should remain constant. Like the area of Bazar should not change, but changes should come in areas where there are problems”

“Natural things about Ravangla should remain natural”.

Why do people believe it is possible?

First of all, Ravangla is a transitioning place, which has changed a lot and is still changing, so people believe that we still have time to preserve some things and change some things about Ravangla. Peace and nature was mentioned by the locals as the essential characteristics of Ravangla, which differentiates this place from other places and makes them feel connected with the city. These two things remained constant among responses talking about preserving things. On the other hand, they wished to see growth in the city, growth as in bigger hospitals with necessary facilities available in Ravangla only, the need for public spaces and urban planning. The locals mentioned that nowadays they are facing water shortage, which was rare back in the days, so this has triggered consciousness for the need of urban planning, the necessary steps needed to solve it and so on. Locals responded that they wanted development in areas where there has been a constant need, like better medical facilities, colleges (higher education institutions) and so on.

This hope can remain alive if, *“We start voicing our opinions on crucial issues about Ravangla. The hope can remain alive if we work hard to keep this place clean, preserve the culture of this place and protect its nature.”* This response sums up the locals' opinions since it is truly important and necessary for us, the locals, to voice our opinions about important things going on. We know

DREAMS FOR TOMORROW

our city best, and we should shape the city in a way that is inclusive, not just to us but also inclusive enough to house local culture, practices, nature, sustainable development and the well-being of the locals.

Conditions for Hope

Recurring dreams for this city, when interviewed, were not for malls and urban commercial infrastructures, which I had anticipated, since these are the spaces we mention in cities. The dreams locals had for this place were filled with a mix of 'it is good now too, but these things can be better'; the good part of Ravangla had peace, friendly people and nature in it, while the 'it can be better' part had the need for higher education institutions, the need for facilitated hospitals and public parks with a siting area in the market. The locals stated that having an approachable committee or a suggestion box can help the authorities learn about the problems of the city and suggestions for the city. They mentioned that they are either not self-aware about whom to approach and the procedure for it, nor do they mention taking part in any change-related activity in Ravangla, except for the older generation interviewees, who mentioned being part of meetings held for change (to make the plaza usable, a meeting was conducted), but they mentioned that the actual impact hasn't happened through it yet.

Main reform should be in policy formulation since projects about the city, on the city, are happening away from that city; no prior area studies are conducted except for the physical area study. An inclusive demographic study, keeping in mind the sociological aspects, is very important to really know what is needed in an area. Questions like where it is needed, who needs it the most and what might happen after should be dealt with. If these questions are kept in mind before executing any kind of change, from regulatory policy to reformative one, problems of unused infrastructure might not arise in the first place. There is a need for vocal public bodies to raise questions and hold conferences in the city to raise issues and awareness.

As mentioned, Ravangla is a transitioning place, so there is still time for changes to happen here, actual changes. In cities like Gangtok, urban planning and regulations is very hard since the area there is very populated, but in Ravangla, there are opportunities and spaces available for change.

Reflection

What is in the way of us realising our City's dreams?

Active participation in the shaping of the city is what I felt was necessary for us to realise our city dreams after talking with the locals. We need higher education institutions to educate the local students, we need facilitated hospitals so that the people of Ravangla don't have to wait to reach Namchi, Gangtok or Siliguri for advanced medical treatments and diagnosis. To realise all these dreams, we, the locals, have to voice out our needs and then look for solutions through the official bodies.

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Policy Insights

Policy Insights

Mobility and accessibility within the city

Most of the locals in Ravangla prefer to walk if the distance to their destination is walkable. The taxis are available, but during the tourist season, the locals face taxi problems. Most of the locals have started buying private vehicles, once they can afford them, but they prefer to walk within Ravangla.

Maintenance and management of public spaces

The market areas are maintained by the Urban Development Department and the bazaar committee, but the drainage issues, mentioned by the interviewees as well, have remained unfixed. The market area hasn't seen many changes except for the setup of railings dividing the road and footpath area.

Protection of cultural and social infrastructure

The Gumpa area, which has many historical monasteries, is maintained by the Ecclesiastical department of Sikkim, with local authorities appointed for the work.

Environmental health and urban commons

Citizen participation and communication with local authorities

The samaj heads, as well as people belonging to community organisations, remain in constant touch with the Member of the Legislative Assembly from Ravangla and other local authorities. They play an important role if the city faces any grave incidents, and the solutions to them come fast, too. However, there are some issues too which face delays in solutions, or the problems are not raised at all.

Possible Policy Directions

Short-Term Improvements

The regulatory policies, including traffic rules and practices affecting parking problems and so on, should be practised regularly with seriousness.

Medium-Term Improvements

Solutions to make the unused infrastructure functional require coordination from all sections of locals, from Ravangla. Their participation will help to bring change to Ravangla.

Long-Term Structural Changes

More investment is needed in future public infrastructure with a serious approach, so that Ravangla can avoid any future examples of the unused plaza.

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Anisha is from Ravangla, Sikkim and is a Political Science scholar with a Master's degree completed and recently qualified for PhD admission through the UGC-NET examination (June 2025). With a strong academic foundation in political science, Anisha brings intellectual rigor and research-oriented thinking to her work. She is passionate about understanding contemporary political issues and contributing to policy-relevant research that addresses societal challenges through scholarly inquiry.

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Message from the Founders

Ten years ago, we set off on a journey across India's small towns. Over five months and fifty cities, we came through stories, crafts, silences, and dreams. We rediscovered that our smaller cities were not merely settlements; they were living archives of collective memory and identity—fossils of space and time inhabited by breath and imagination.

In Ratnagiri we were directed by many city experts to meet an auto mechanic. He was the go-to person for everyone in the city, including the city government, for engineering issues such as the city's water supply. He had seen the city evolve and remembered its various extensions, its water supply networks, and the various issues the city had faced in the last few decades. In Thanjavur, we sat with a veena-maker working 20-hour days in a modest shed, carving centuries of musical tradition into a single piece of jackfruit wood. We listened to bakers, poets, priests, and students. They told us not only what their cities were, but what they could become.

What struck us most was this: citizens carry the city's soul. The insights they hold—about its past, its present, and its future—are powerful, yet rarely represented in how cities are imagined or governed. This realization gave genesis to the Nāgrika Fellowship. It has been our attempt to honour the power of local voices—to create space for young people to observe, listen, document, and co-create city narratives from within. Each City Vision Document is not just a reflection of one fellow's journey; it's a collaborative act of remembering and imagining.

We hope this document stirs dialogue, ownership, and pride. And just like cities that shape their people, we hope this fellowship shapes a new kind of citizen—curious, rooted, and ready to lead.

We exist to ensure small-city voices, often unheard, have the knowledge and tools to influence the development and policies of their communities.

We focus on citizen-driven research. By engaging directly with small city communities, we present their authentic realities, untouched by outside narratives. This hands-on approach keeps small city voices at the heart of everything we do.

Citizen-Centred

It's always about the people. Small-city citizens are at the heart of everything we do.

Curious and Objective

Our approach stems from curiosity—focusing on the truth, making sure every voice in small cities is heard clearly and fairly.

Credible and Rooted

We are committed to producing knowledge and insight from the small cities that is dependable and high-quality.

Resourceful

We make the most of what we have, using our resources wisely to create valuable knowledge.

Small Cities, Big Love

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